

WIDE BAND MODULATION OF CONDUCTED SUSCEPTIBILITY SIGNALS

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ABSTRACT

The concept of Wide Band Modulation of a Bulk Cable Injected, Conducted Susceptibility Signal is explored in this paper as a complement to frequency stirring below the frequencies where uniform radiated fields can not be produced. The method is especially useful for long cycle time test articles. The study suggests a suitable modulation and scan rate as an initial look. The technique was then used to identify susceptibilities in a long cycle time test article and its effectiveness was compared to existing technology. The results strongly indicate that this is an excellent screening tool to identify potential susceptibility areas rapidly and then use conventional methodology to better characterize the responses. The results indicate that the methodology could be used to replace conventional methods in completely characterizing the test article, however, the results were not thoroughly conclusive. Further investigation and refinement of the methodology will be necessary.

BACKGROUND

Band Limited White Gaussian Noise Modulation or frequency stirring was developed and discussed in reference (a) as an alternate method of performing radiated susceptibility testing. This methodology has been tried and proven with the results and discussion provided in references (b) and (c). Frequency stirring has been demonstrated to increase scan rate up to a factor of 200 under certain conditions. This is especially significant with test articles that have very long cycle times, because scan speeds should be adjusted inversely proportional to the cycle times to assure that all events in the cycle are properly exposed. Unfortunately, frequency stirring is not as effective below frequencies (typically 200 MHz) that do not support the modal structure density necessary for a uniform field.

Presently, proper susceptibility evaluation of long cycle time test articles is a rarity, so it is an important concept. The consequences of improper evaluation

can only be speculated, but ultimately can lead to loss of valuable equipment and even personnel.

This investigation was limited due to time constraints, test artifact life expectancy and availability of resources (suitable test artifacts and modulation equipment), however, the following will be examined to the degrees possible:

- a) recommended bandwidths and the associated levels necessary
- b) a comparison of different modulation and levels necessary to produce equivalent susceptibility response
- c) the effectiveness of identifying susceptibilities of a long cycle time test item and comparison to conventional methods.

DESCRIPTION OF EQUIPMENT UNDER TEST

The Equipment Under Test (EUT) was a portable X-ray imaging system used to X-ray objects for security purposes. The EUT consisted of a computer, an X-ray generator, an X-ray imager, 120 feet of shielded cable, connecting the imager to the computer and 10 feet of unshielded cable connecting the X-ray generator to the X-ray imager. The EUT used 115V AC power feeding the computer and the X-ray generator. The EUT had an exceptionally long cycle associated with the firing and data acquisition of the image. Acquisition time is controlled by the operator depending on the level of detail needed in the image.

SCOPE OF TEST

Bulk Cable Injected Conducted Susceptibility testing was performed on the EUT to the limits of reference (d), Test Method CS114 from 2 MHz to 400 MHz and to the associated methodology in reference (e). The only departure from the Test Method procedures was the use of wide band modulation and a change in scan rates. The limit for the injected current is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1, CS114 Test Limit

TEST SET UP

The EUT was set up in a typical RF shielded enclosure. Since the equipment was considered portable, the unit was not bonded other than through the safety ground in the power cord, nor was a ground plane used. The computer, X-ray generator and X-ray imager were each placed on non-conductive, non-absorbing crates. The cable was partially suspended above the room's conductive floor and the remaining cable laid directly on the floor to simulate a normal operation set up. Testing was performed with an "EUT, 30 second acquisition macro" in operation. The equipment configuration is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2, Equipment test set up

FAILURE CRITERIA

The EUT was considered to be susceptible when the video on the computer was significantly degraded, the X-ray image was significantly degraded, or if the

controller macro was interrupted, stalled, or exhibited a system error.

TEST METHODOLOGY

Test preparation required identification of scan times, modulation parameters and bandwidths to be used for the testing of the EUT.

Modulation

The modulation scheme was originally intended to be double side band, carrier suppressed modulation with white gaussian noise. The equipment for performing this modulation was not available for the testing in this frequency range, thus a high deviation constant, FM modulation was chosen as an alternate modulation scheme.

Scan Rates

MIL-STD-462D was the basis for derivation of the scan rates used during the course of this testing. Table 1 presents the scan rate normally used for CS114 testing. The rate is actually continuously variable as noted by the f_0 , however, for simplicity, the initial frequency in the band will be used. The rate is based on an EUT response time of 1 sec. MIL-STD-462D also defines a failure Q that is related to a cross segment of typical EUTs that have been tested for military use in recent years.

FREQUENCY RANGE	Q FACTOR	SCAN RATE
2 MHz-30 MHz	100	20 kHz/sec (.01 f_0 /sec)
30 MHz-400 MHz	200	150 kHz/sec (.005 f_0 /sec)

Table 1 MIL-STD-462 Recommended Scan Rates 1 sec EUT Response Time

Failure bandwidths in Table 2 were derived directly from the Q values associated with MIL-STD-462D. The failure bandwidth was calculated from $FBW=f_0/Q$. These are considered typical.

Frequency Range (MHz)	MIL-STD-462D Typical Failure Bandwidth (kHz)	Scan Rate 30 sec EUT response (kHz/Sec)
2-30	20	1.33
30-100	150	10
100-250	500	33.33
250-400	1,250	83.33

Table 2 Adjusted 30 Sec EUT Response Time Scan Rates

The susceptibility signal must remain in the EUT failure bandwidth for at least the response time of the EUT, thus the scan rates in Table 2 (scan rate = FBW/EUT response time). The two frequency bands normally specified for the test were further broken into 4 bands to optimize scan rates for the wide band FM. The same Q value was used from the original bands, however, the start frequency of the new band was used to calculate the failure bandwidth and thus, the scan rate for the additional bands. From these bandwidths, new scan rates were derived assuming that the failure bandwidth must remain in the EUT band pass for 30 sec. The rate can be further adjusted to account for energy differences between using pulse modulation and FM. The 50% duty cycle when using pulse modulation results in a 50% reduction of the total power used for FM. Assuming the EUT is time averaging due to the long cycle time, the scan rate can be increased by a factor of 2.

Theoretically, these rates are the maximum that can be used regardless of the use of broadband signals. Practically, the rate can be much faster because of a number of factors:

a) The EUT response is never defined by a theoretical step response function, i.e. the EUT will still respond beyond some defined susceptibility bandwidth. The response is usually complex (except intentionally tuned circuits) and can be over a very wide range, but with a resulting change in level.

b) The response will rarely be the full anticipated cycle time. The various events in the cycle often have similar or related response times, so if one is missed one of the others will be identified. Also, if there are slow responding circuits associated with the cycle, they will tend to retain the energy somewhat over the cycle time.

c) Test levels can be increased proportionally by the ratio of the test signal bandwidth to the anticipated susceptibility bandwidth.

The exact effects of these factors can not be exactly quantified, so the increase in rate can not be clearly identified, except as a function of item c). Thus, procedures need to be identified based on more experience with equipment responses to wide band susceptibility signals. For this evaluation, these rates were used as a minimum starting point.

Calibration

Prior to testing, the injection probe and cables were calibrated to determine the power level required to attain the reference (d) test limit for curve 5 with a 100 Ω loop. The calibration configuration is as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 CS114 Wide band Calibration Set up

These values are provided in Table 3 along with modulation parameters necessary to achieve the desired bandwidths. The calibration levels were performed in discrete steps and at those frequencies, the level was increased until the desired current level was obtained. The desired current level was monitored by noting the equivalent 50 Ω power level of the spectrum analyzer. The objective for the modulation was to identify parameters that would provide the flattest amplitude versus frequency response possible. These were identified primarily by trial and error since side bands associated with FM do not necessarily produce flat amplitude response. With the equipment used, a 3dB flatness in the amplitude response was the acceptance criteria. The waveform verification bandwidths were chosen so as to provide suitable resolution of the waveform. The test level verification waveform bandwidths were chosen at the minimum bandwidth that would resolve the wide band signal level equal to a continuous wave signal. A peak power meter measurement was also made to assure agreement. In

WIDE BAND FM, BULK CABLE INJECTION MODULATION AND LEVEL TABLE
(Fischer F-51 Monitor and F-130-1 Injection Probes)

Frequency MHz	Calculated Default Failure Bandwidth (MHz)	FM Deviation constant (kHz)	Mod level (volts)	Mod frequency (kHz)	RBW/VBW Waveform verification kHz/kHz	RBW Test level Verification kHz/kHz	Injected Current level (dBμA)	Calculated/ Actual power -50 dB to produce level (dBm)	Calibration power -30 dB spectrum analyzer (dBm)	Monitor Probe reading dBμV
2	.020	15	0.3	1.0	3/3	50/3	109.0	4.5/3.14	6.0	119.0
3	.020	15	0.3	1.0	3/3	50/3	109.0	1.5/-1.12	6.0	122.0
4	.020	15	0.3	1.0	3/3	50/3	109.0	-0.5/-2.2	6.0	123.0
5	.020	15	0.3	1.0	3/3	50/3	109.0	-1.7-4.5	6.0	123.7
6	.020	15	0.3	1.0	3/3	50/3	109.0	-2.5/-5.7	6.0	124.2
8	.020	15	0.3	1.0	3/3	50/3	109.0	-3.9/-7.3	6.0	125.2
10	.020	15	0.3	1.0	3/3	50/3	109.0	-5.5/-8.2	6.0	125.8
20	.020	15	0.3	1.0	3/3	50/3	109.0	-6.0/-9.8	6.0	127.0
30	0.30	55	0.5	1.0	30/30	500/1	109.0	-6.0/-9.9	6.0	127.7
40	0.30	55	0.5	1.0	30/30	500/1	108.0	-7.0/-0.2	5.0	127.0
50	0.30	55	0.5	1.0	30/30	500/1	106.5	-8.5/-2.2	3.5	125.5
60	0.30	55	0.5	1.0	30/30	500/1	105.5	-9.5/-3.2	2.5	124.5
80	0.30	55	0.5	1.0	30/30	500/1	104.0	-11/-14.4	1.0	123.0
100	1.0	71	1.1	1.2	30/30	1250/1	103.0	-12/-15.6	0.0	122.0
150	1.0	78	1.1	2	30/30	1250/10	101.0	-14/-18.2	-2.0	120.0
200	1.25	165	1.1	5	30/30	1500/30	100.0	-15-18.3	-3.0	119.0
250	1.25	165	0.9	6	30/30	1500/30	99.5	-15.5/-18.3	-3.5	118.5
300	1.25	165	0.9	6	30/30	1500/30	98.5	-16.5/-19.6	-4.5	117.5
350	1.25	165	0.9	6	30/30	1500/30	97.5	-17.5/-20.7	-5.5	116.5
400	1.25	165	0.9	6	30/30	1500/30	97.0	-18.0/-21.7	-7.0	116.0

Monitored specification limit current converted to volts dBμV (spec an)=dBμA+probe transfer impedance
 Monitored calibration power into spectrum analyzer dBm(-30 dB)=dBμA-73-30 (attenuator)
 Calculated power into circuit dBm(-50dB)=dBμA-73+3(correction to 100Ω)-50(attenuator)+probe insertion loss

Table 3, MODIFIED CS114 MODULATION AND LEVEL TABLE

order to accomplish this, a fair amount of video filtering was necessary to smooth the response to keep it from jumping between peak read levels. The calculated/actual power column provides the data that was calculated as necessary to produce the required level into the 100 Ω loop and the actual power that was needed. This represents the total power into the circuit including the injection probe losses. The calibration power is the power that feeds into the spectrum analyzer in the 100 Ω calibration loop. The monitor probe reading is the anticipated value that the monitor probe would see accounting for probe losses and assuming the test circuit was 100 Ω . The actual power into the calibration circuit along with the monitor probe reading become the test levels to be monitored. The objective is to meet the monitor probe reading (equivalent to the test level current in the circuit), if the actual power into the circuit is not exceeded.

Test Procedure

Using the test limits and modulation identified in Table 3, the EUT was scanned over the frequency range of interest. Note that this was a departure from the scan rates and bandwidths identified in Table 2 for the frequency range of 30-250 MHz. However, this provided additional evidence that larger bandwidths could be successfully used. The signal was injected into the circuit using the current injection probe. The synthesizer was constantly leveled to maintain the specified power level and/or current limit in the appropriate frequency band. Since this test procedure is not presently automated in our laboratory, it was extremely difficult to calculate and monitor the true specification limit continuously as this value realistically must be calculated at each frequency to provide a continuous function. Instead, the limit was calculated at the frequencies shown in Table 3 and this value was used up to the next frequency in the table. Thus, at the end frequency for a particular band, the test limit was slightly higher than the true test limit. The level was monitored as a voltage with another induction probe. The current was calculated directly from the probe voltage using the equation in Table 3 and the probe calibration factors. When a susceptibility was identified, the failure bandwidth was noted.

RESULTS

A validation of the modified test methodology was performed in a two part process. One part was a validation of the EUT susceptibility comparing 2 wide band FM modulated scans with the normal MIL-STD-461D scan (rates as identified in Table 1). The data is

provided in Table 4. Only a limited range was examined due to the lack of time. In general, there was good agreement. The extent to which they did not agree may be attributed to several factors. The most obvious factor is the failure bandwidth. From Table 4, it is apparent that the MIL-STD-461D methodology identified more areas of susceptibility. It appears that the bandwidth of the FM was in many instances larger than the failure bandwidth, so naturally these areas would be expected to have a somewhat higher threshold with this form of modulation. This is a direct result of not all the energy being in the failure bandwidth. The susceptibilities most likely could have been identified with a higher level. The in-band argument is also complicated as the EUT failure response is not truly a function of note bandwidths. In actuality, the response was varying widely with frequency and seemingly ever present, so a true comparison is related to the integral of the susceptibility response compared to the integral of the susceptibility signal in the frequency range of the susceptibility signal. However, this does not appear to be the most significant factor, as the 1 MHz bandwidth FM signal did not really identify that many more susceptibilities than the 3 MHz bandwidth. The scan rate might also be a factor as faster scan rates might miss slower responding susceptibilities. This does not seem to be a significant factor, as the EUT video appeared to respond instantaneously with a resultant stored image (30 sec response) captured consistently. Finally, the susceptibility of the EUT apparently would change with temperature. There were instances when a frequency band was known to be a susceptible region, but when testing on start up, the failure region could not be repeated. The MIL-STD-461D scan was performed after the EUT was on for 8 hours, so the EUT was much warmer than at the other scans. This was somewhat validated by verifying that the wide band FM did produce a susceptibility response during the MIL-STD-462D scan from 164.5 MHz on. Not only was the signal verified statically, but a "mini rescan" was performed at these points to assure it was not a function of the scan rate missing the susceptibility. As failures were identified with the slower MIL-STD-461 rate, the modulation and scan rate were changed back to the widest FM modulation and fastest scan rate and the susceptibility was clearly evident. As a comparison of actual scan time, the MIL-STD-461 rate takes 6.8 hours, the wide band FM, 1 MHz bandwidth scan took 3.1 hours of scan time and the wide band FM 3 MHz bandwidth takes about 6 minutes (actual time was much greater due to data taking and set up changes).

Another validation was performed by simple comparison of various modulations schemes to determine similarity

1 MHz bandwidth, 33 kHz/sec rate, wide band FM	3 MHz bandwidth, 1 MHz/sec rate, wide band FM	Pulse modulation, 1 kHz, 50% duty cycle MIL-STD-461D rates/30
	83.4-84.5	83.7-84.9
88.5-89.8	86.7-89.8	87-87.8
		88.7-89.7
		91.4-91.6
93.4-95.8	93.1-96.2	93.6-95.6
98.7-104	98-101.6	98.7-102.5
		104.6-104.9
105.6-108.8	105-112	106-113.6
110-113.7	112.8-117	114.5-117.3
		117.8-118.7
114-117		
120.6-122.4	122-122.6	120.8-122.3
		124.7-125.4
		126.3-126.9
		164.5-168.8, verified with FM, 3 MHz
		217.7-219.1, verified with FM, 3 MHz
		222.7-223.5, not repeatable with FM, 3 MHz
229.3-231.5	229.5-?	229.5-231.5, verified with FM, 3 MHz
234.3-237.5		234.8-240, verified with FM, 3 MHz
		243-244.1, verified with FM, 3 MHz
248.5-258.7	249-253	247.9-255.5, verified with FM, 3 MHz
260.5-266.3	262-264	257.1-265.8, verified with FM, 3 MHz
		267.9-269.2, verified with FM, 3 MHz
		278.3-278.7, verified with FM, 3 MHz
280.2-282.7	280-283	281.3-283.6, verified with FM, 3 MHz
289.8-290		289.5-292.1, verified with FM, 3 MHz
		297.6-298, near threshold of FM, 3 MHz
363.2-366.5	?-365	364.2-364.8, verified with FM, 3 MHz

Table 4 Comparison Of Scan Rates In Determining Failures And Failure Bandwidths

of response and threshold to MIL-STD-462D modulation. Table 5 provides the results of comparing various modulations to determine the threshold of the susceptibility response. The results demonstrated that the susceptibility using wide band FM with the larger bandwidths produced nearly identical results to the 1 kHz pulse modulation normally used for CS114 testing. However, the table indicated that it was critical to use the widest bandwidth allowable by the synthesizer for a given frequency band. Smaller bandwidths produced a response closer to CW. This was exactly the results needed, because the wide band test concept relied on a modulation bandwidth as wide as possible. The modulation signal voltage was maintained constant at 1 volt for the various modulations. The deviation constant was varied to produce the necessary FM bandwidth. In all, the validation demonstrated that the wide band FM was an excellent tool for performing the evaluation and was also very useful for screening purposes.

CONCLUSIONS

The wide band modulation characterized the test item efficiently. In fact, the scan rate was increased by a factor of 68 and susceptibilities were still being identified. It was inconclusive whether the wide band modulation technique characterized the unit as thoroughly as with the MIL-STD-462D modulation. The actual scan comparison indicated that susceptibilities were being missed, but rechecks at various susceptibility points demonstrated excellent identification of susceptibilities. However, the results clearly demonstrate tremendous potential as a screening tool to use the method for quick scanning. Using a higher power levels than the test limit, with bandwidths wider than the calculated failure bandwidths, potential areas of susceptibility can be identified and then better characterized with conventional methodology. Better yet, the methodology could be optimized from better knowledge of the EUT's calculated response characteristics. Considering the time element and cost benefits for a given scan rate, the wide band modulation will characterize a long cycle time EUT faster. This is invaluable in the EMI community, since long scan rates, slow enough to properly characterize the test item are often cost prohibitive.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This was a limited "proof of concept" investigation, so considerable investigation with various EUTs and/or with or a "controllable/characterized" EUT is needed to develop suitable procedures for identification of

bandwidths, levels and scan rates for a particular EUT. The methodology should not be used as a replacement until further study is conducted. However, since this study did indicate a significant time and cost savings, additional study is highly encouraged. Gaussian noise double side band, carrier suppressed modulation should be examined in order to obtain larger bandwidths and flatter response. An automated system is also highly recommended to obtain better control of the test instrumentation.

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	Video Susceptibility Threshold at Frequency (dB μ V)					
	90 MHz	100 MHz	122 MHz	220 MHz	300 MHz	365 MHz
FM, 100 kHz bandwidth	122	125	130	N/A	N/A	N/A
FM, 300/500 kHz bandwidth	114	120	122	125	120	130
FM, 1 MHz bandwidth	114	116	122	115	111	108
FM, 3 MHz bandwidth	N/A	N/A	N/A	112	108	98
AM, 1 kHz	114	116	132	119	107	98
AM, 10 kHz	114	115	129	117	109	97
Continuous wave	123*	124*	135*	132*	122*	133
Square wave AM, 10 kHz	113	115	129	115	107	98
Pulse mod 1 kHz, 50%	113	115	127	115	105	98
Pulse mod 10 kHz, 50%	113	115	128	115	106	97

*Not susceptible at the limit noted, power levels from amplifier getting too high.

TABLE 5, COMPARISON OF SUSCEPTIBILITY THRESHOLDS FOR VARIOUS MODULATIONS